

Handling of research data when writing a PhD dissertation.

Once collected in the context of the doctoral thesis, data are processed and reused, and here new tasks arise in the context of research data management (RDM).

The doctoral students are responsible for their own data and the management of data.

The University Library of Hildesheim supports the doctoral students in all areas of RDM as well as other members of the university.

During the support service, it is first of all very important to clarify what experience the doctoral candidate has with regards to methods, creation or use of software and data?

What steps must be taken w.r.t. RDM?

What kind of data are collected?

Research data

- Primary text sources (also in digital form)
- Audiovisual information
- Survey data and the corresponding questionnaires
- Photos
- Maps (analog)
- Data generated in the field of geographical information systems (GIS) and the underlying raw data
- Climate and weather data
- Astrophysical observations
- Digitised objects from collections

- Measured data from laboratory or analysis equipment
- Images from visual analysis methods
- Developed software
- Scripts
- Illustrations/graphics
- Maps (digital)
- Models
- Simulations

GitHub/GitLab

Git is ideal for text-based files such as code/scripts or LATEX files.

Research Software

Research software is an integral part of the research process and important for the traceability of research results. The software can be part of the results and should be included in the scientific discourse.

Legal framework and research ethical issues must be clarified

Under what conditions are data generated?

Who are the persons with whom the planned usage must be coordinated?

Consent and licenses play an important role.

Documentation

Research data should be well documented!

Publication

With Dataverse, researchers can permanently secure their research data and make data publicly available (publish), open access, in a sustainable and high-quality manner.

The research data are given a persistent identifier when they are published in this repository.

Archiving

“Researchers back up research data and results made publicly available, as well as the central materials on which they are based and the research software used, by adequate means according to the standards of the relevant subject area, and retain them for an appropriate period of time. Where justifiable reasons exist for not archiving particular data, researchers explain these reasons. HEIs and non-HEI research institutions ensure that the infrastructure necessary to enable archiving is in place.

Explanations: When scientific and academic findings are made publicly available, the research data (generally raw data) on which they are based are generally archived in an accessible and identifiable manner for a period of ten years at the institution where the data were produced or in cross-location repositories. This practice may differ depending on the subject area. In justified cases, shorter archiving periods may be appropriate; the reasons for this are described clearly and comprehensibly. The archiving period begins on the date when the results are made publicly available (DFG Code of Conduct, Guideline 17).”¹

Where there are reasonable grounds for not keeping certain data, this must be explained. The long-term archiving of research data is a prerequisite for the traceability and verifiability of scientific results based on the evaluation of these data. Research data are visible and appreciated as independent scientific achievements.

When it goes beyond the temporary storage of work files that are created during the research process and is about preserving the research data (archiving in accordance with good scientific practice, DFG Code of Conduct) and digital long-term archiving, subject-specific repositories or research data centres are generally used because they are better perceived by the subject community.

Good scientific practice

It is recommended to make research data/research software and scientific publications publicly available in accordance with the Open Access guidelines of the University of

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https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/rechtliche_rahmenbedingungen/gute_wissenschaftliche_praxis/kodex_gwp_en.pdf (21.07.2020)

Hildesheim Foundation. For this purpose, we advise to choose an open license (e.g. Creative Commons) for easy re-use. This is done in consideration of the requirements of the research funding agencies and partners. The FAIR Data Principles as well as the software and data citation principles are always considered.

Literature (in German)

Strauch, A. (2020). Universitätsbibliotheken heute. Partner im Forschungsdatenmanagement in der Praxis, *ABI Technik*, 40(2), 177-186. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1515/abitech-2020-2008>

Strauch, A. (2019). Forschungsdatenmanagement an der Stiftung Universität Hildesheim, *Information - Wissenschaft & Praxis*, 70(5-6), 259-263. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1515/iwp-2019-2052>

Strauch, A. (2019). Forschungsdatenmanagement sozialwissenschaftlicher Umfragedaten: Grundlagen und praktische Lösungen für den Umgang mit quantitativen Forschungsdaten Jensen Uwe, Netscher S., & Weller K. (Herausgeber) – Opladen, Berlin, Toronto: Verlag Barbara Budrich, 2019, 233 S. ISBN: 3847422332, *Information - Wissenschaft & Praxis*, 70(5-6), 306-307. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1515/iwp-2019-2044>